

MATERIALS RESPONSE OF C/C COMPOSITES UNDER LATERAL VIBRATION

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ABSTRACT

As potential materials for fusion reactors, space power generators and for other severe environments, C/C composites have to be provided many properties required. Materials response under applied vibration is very important to understand baseline mechanical properties. A newly developed internal friction apparatus in a vacuum is applied to C/C composites, where three internal friction peaks were identified between room temperature and 1373 K. These peaks are interpreted to be related with the gas desorption from the C/C composites. The micro crack formation to connect closed pores to open pores was suggested to be an important part of those peak formation.

Keywords:

C/C composites, internal friction, Young's modulus, gas desorption, microstructure, pore, lateral vibration, elevated temperature properties

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon/Carbon composite (C/C composite) materials are very important potential materials for space planes, hyper-sonic transports, fusion reactors and other applications under very severe environments[1,2]. Although, there have been many intensive works on these materials, even standardization of test methods to evaluate many baseline mechanical properties has not been established.

Internal friction measurement methods have been recognized to be important methods to obtain basic understandings of those structurally and chemically complex materials and have been providing many important information about elastic and pseudo-elastic regimes [3]. In this study, a newly developed lateral vibration type internal friction measurement apparatus by electrostatic capacitance method with an advanced high temperature capability [4] was applied to two-dimensional (2D) C/C composites.

The purpose of this study is to provide materials response of C/C composites under lateral vibration with small amplitude. The main emphasis is the relation between gas desorption and internal friction. The gas desorption behavior together with pore configuration in the C/C composites is known to be important to evaluate baseline mechanical properties in a vacuum and at very high temperatures [5-8]. But up to now, no clear understandings

about relations among internal friction, gas desorption and mechanical properties have been established.

2. EXPERIMENTALS

2.1. Internal Friction Measurement

Internal friction measurement was carried out utilizing the recently developed lateral vibration type internal friction apparatus by electrostatic capacitance method with an advanced high temperature capability and clean vacuum [1]. The temperature range for this measurement was from 298 K (room temperature;RT) to 1373 K and a vacuum quality at RT was 2×10^{-5} Pa and was 3×10^{-3} Pa at 1373 K. There is a gas inlet line to change atmosphere of the vacuum chamber, such as Air, N_2 and Ar. Quadrapole type mass analyzer is attached to the chamber which enable to analyze gases with mass to charge ratio up to 90. Specimen setting scheme is illustrated in Figure 1. Bar type specimen is placed the center of the setting stage, hung by W wire about 0.5 mm above the driver and detector electrodes. The specimen size flexibility ranges from 45 to 100, 2 to 10 and 0.3 to 2 mm, for length, width and thickness, respectively.

Young's modulus (E) of C/C composites was determined with resonant frequency (f) from the following equation.

$$E \text{ (GPa)} = 0.94668 \times 10^{-9} \times \left(\frac{l}{t}\right)^3 \left(\frac{M}{w}\right) f^2 \quad (1)$$

where, t, w, l and M is specimen thickness, width, length in mm and mass in gram, respectively.

Internal friction value was determined from free attenuation behavior under lateral vibration with an strain amplitude about 10^{-5} . Figure 2 is a schematic presentatio n of resonant vibration indicating free attenuation behavior. From amplitudes of specific waves, i.e. θ_m , θ_{m+1} and θ_n , logarithmic attenuation fraction, δ , can be obtained as follows.

$$\delta = \ln \frac{\theta_m}{\theta_{m+1}} = \frac{\ln(\theta_m / \theta_n)}{n - m} \quad (2)$$

where n and m denotes the number of waves in order, thus, (n-m) is the number of waves counted.

Figure 1. Specimen setting arrangement for measurement.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of resonant vibration indicating free attenuation behavior.

Then internal friction, Q^{-1} , is defined as,

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{\delta}{\pi} = \frac{\ln(\theta_m/\theta_n)}{\pi(n-m)} \quad (3)$$

2.2. Materials

Materials used in this work are PAN type fiber reinforced C/C composites. The representing characteristics are summarized in Table 1. Prepreg sheets of flat woven fabrics impregnated with phenolic resin were stacked and pyrolyzed to form C/C composites. Impregnation and pyrolysis process were repeated for densification of C/C composites. The final heat treatment temperature was 1873 K. The specimens for internal friction measurement were saw cut from the as fabricated sheets and followed by polishing to become the final dimensions of 1 mm in thickness, 5 mm in width and 80 mm in length.

Table 1. Representing characteristics of the C/C composite used.

Carbon fiber for reinforcement	PAN type continuous fibers 7 μ m in diameter 3.6GPa in tensile strength 240GPa in elastic modulus 1.77 in specific weight
Reinforcement	Flat woven fabrics (420/420; yarn/m) 6000 fibers/yarn
Matrix	Carbonized phenolic resin

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Temperature Dependence of Young's Modulus and Internal Friction

Temperature spectra of Young's modulus and internal friction are shown in Figure 3. Young's modulus indicates slightly positive temperature dependence, that is with increasing temperature it increases a little. This behavior has been analyzed and interpreted through

degree of graphitization in reference [9] where the authors summarizes the behavior that with increasing graphitization degree the positive temperature dependence tends to shifts to negative.

The internal friction spectrum measured presents three peaks at about 310, 380 and 610 K. These peaks are denoted as Peak I, II and III, respectively. To investigate temperature history effects on those peaks, sequential measurement was performed and its results are shown in Figure 4. The sequential measurement is designed to change maximum temperature, shown as end of run temperature in Figure 4, for each measurement run with 523, 773, 1073 and 1373 K end of run temperature. After the first run, that is the second run, Peak I and II were annihilated. After the second run, i.e. the third run, Peak III was reduced its peak height to nearly half. Then after the third run, those peaks were diminished. This means that those peaks are connected with thermal annealing or thermally recovering processes. And by the

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus and internal friction in C/C composite.

Figure 4. Temperature spectra of internal friction under successive measurements from room temperature to the different end-of-run temperatures(T_{EOR}).

thermal history with the maximum temperature of 1373 K every origins to form those peaks are apparently disappeared. In this case, the materials used was heat treated at 1873 K which means that the thermal history with the maximum temperature of 1373 K would produce little microstructural change. Thus, behavior of gases inside and at the surface of C/C composites draw our attention to solve the mechanism of those peaks.

3.2. Characteristics of The Peaks

In order to investigate the role of gases to the three peak formation, simultaneous gas analysis during the internal friction measurement was carried out. Figure 5 summarizes the gas desorption behavior at each of the three peak. In this figure, H₂, O, OH, NH₃, H₂O, CO, N₂ and O₂ were detected. Mass spectrum at 308 K, shown in Figure 5, has no difference within the resolution of the mass spectroscopy used. That is, by the thermal history up to 308 K, no significant gas desorption would exist. Still the fact that the Peak I diminished after heating up to 308 K and was appeared after exposure in air seems to indicate very weakly adsorpted gases is responsible to this peak. At Peak II temperature and Peak III temperature, dominant part of the desorption gases can be identified to be H₂O and CO+N₂, respectively. Therefore, desorption spectra of H₂O and CO+N₂ were measured. From the comparisons of desorption spectra with and without C/C composites in the chamber, desorption spectra from C/C composites were obtained and they are shown in Figure 6. The temperature wise coincidence of H₂O gas desorption and the Peak II seems to indicate that the Peak II corresponds H₂O gas desorption. This gas desorption behavior is coincided well with the results of Hino *et al.*[10]. The slight but clear increase of gas desorption at temperature higher than 610 K corresponds the peak temperature of the Peak III. This peak is known to be enhanced under excess nitrogen contents in C/C composites (8) suggesting the Peak III seems to be connected with gas desorption of N₂ rather than of CO. It might lead to the possibility that the Peak II is connected with CO gas.

Figure 5. Mass spectra of desorption gas for C/C composite at the temperatures of peaks I,II and III, shown in Figure 3.

Figure 6. Gas desorption behaviors under the heating of 3K/min.; (a)H₂O and CO+N₂.

3.3. Gas Desorption Behavior and Internal Friction

Due to the conclusion that the three peaks observed in C/C composites might be connected with gas desorption, gas desorption behavior under internal friction measurement at each peak temperature was investigated. The results for the Peak II and for the Peak III are shown in Figure 7. Both for the two cases, internal friction gradually decrease with time for internal friction measurement. Especially for the case of the Peak III temperature, the value monotonically decreases. On the other hand, for the case of the Peak II temperature, periodical increase is overlapped to the monotonical drop. In Figure 8, the gas desorption behavior of H₂O and internal friction are shown. There is a quite good coincidence of the cyclic behavior of both properties with roughly 18 min. intervals. The duration and the amount of internal friction suggests a strong linkage between gas desorption and internal friction and as to the cyclic behavior gas desorption from closed pore is supposed to be an potential origin. This cyclic behaviors became smaller with continuation of measurement and over about 4 hours, the periodic behavior became almost undetectable and the decrease of internal friction and gas desorption became monotonical. Figure 9 is a typical microstructure of C/C composite indicating the configuration of pores. In general, large pores, as large as several microns, exist in the widely opened portion of the matrix and middle sized pores and small pores, as small as 2 angstrom, exist in the narrow portion of the matrix between fibers. The gas desorption from closed pores might involve two mechanisms; (1) linkage of pore to make a feed through to the surface introduced by lateral vibration of specimens, (2) atomic or gaseous diffusion through matrix to accumulate gas in closed pores. Figure 10 provides a schematic illustration of open pore development behavior. The cyclic behavior about internal friction and gas desorption only seen at Peak II temperature seems to suggest that the open pore development is the dominant mechanism to make such behavior. Because, the smooth and gradual decrease of internal friction and gas desorption is consistent with the fact that crack development in C/C composites should be introduced at lower temperature and diffusion should be accelerated at higher temperature. Although, quantitative analysis of internal friction

and gas desorption is not satisfactory to explain all the details and it is too early to be conclusive about the mechanism of the internal friction spectra.

Figure 7. Internal friction changes during measurement at the temperature of peaks II and III.

Figure 8. Gas desorption behavior of H₂O and internal friction.

Figure 9. TEM micrograph of pores in the matrix of C/C composite.

Figure 10. Schematics of open pore development near surface (a) at room temperature and (b) at 380 K(Peak II).

4. CONCLUSIONS

To understand materials response of C/C composites under lateral vibration with small amplitude, a newly developed lateral vibration type internal friction measurement apparatus by electrostatic capacitance method with an advanced high temperature capability was applied to 2D C/C composites. The conclusions can be summarized as follows.

(1) The internal friction spectra measured present three peaks, denoted as Peak I, Peak II and Peak III, at about 310, 380 and 610 K, respectively. From gas analysis during the internal friction measurement, these peaks are interpreted to be related with the gas desorption from C/C composites.

(2) Very weakly absorbed gases are interpreted to be responsible to those peaks and they are thought to be strongly connected with gas desorption of H_2O and N_2 , for peak 2 and peak 3, respectively, from pores in C/C composites.

(3) The micro crack formation to connect closed pores to open pores was suggested to be an important part of those peak formation.

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